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Figure 1:

- a-b) Rodelli D, Jovane L, Giorgioni M, Rego ES, Cornaggia F, Benites M, Cedraz P, Berbel GBB, Braga ES, Ustra A, Abreu F, Roberts AP (2019) Diagenetic Fate of Biogenic Soft and Hard Magnetite in Chemically Stratified Sedimentary Environments of Mamanguá Ría, Brazil. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth* 124(3):2313–2330. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1029/2018JB016576>
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- d) Hanzlik M, Winklhofer M, Petersen N (2002) Pulsed-field-remnance measurements on individual magnetotactic bacteria. *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials* 248(2):258–267. URL [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-8853\(02\)00353-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-8853(02)00353-0)
- e) Shcherbakov VP, Winklhofer M, Hanzlik M, Petersen N (1997) Elastic stability of chains of magnetosomes in magnetotactic bacteria. *European Biophysics Journal with Biophysics Letters* 26(4):319–326. URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/s002490050086>
- f) Lins U, Farina M (2004) Magnetosome chain arrangement and stability in magnetotactic cocci. *Antonie van Leeuwenhoek* 85:335–341. URL <http://dx.doi.org/B:ANTO.0000020393.71843.b0>
- g) Yamazaki T (2020) Reductive dissolution of biogenic magnetite. *Earth, Planets and Space* 72:150. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s40623-020-01290-3>
- h) Oda H, Nakasato Y, Usui A (2018) Characterization of marine ferromanganese crust from the Pacific using residues of selective chemical leaching: Identification of fossil magnetotactic bacteria with FE-SEM and rock magnetic methods. *Earth, Planets and Space* 70:165. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s40623-018-0924-3>
- i) Courtesy of B. Maher
- j) Thomas-Keprta KL, Bazylinski DA, Kirschvink JL, Clemett SJ, McKay DS, Wentworth SJ, Vali H, Gibson EK, Romanek CS (2000) Elongated prismatic magnetite crystals in ALH84001 carbonate globules: Potential Martian magnetofossils. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* 64(23):4049–4081. URL <http://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.68.8.3663-3672.2002>
- k) Golden DC, Ming DW, Morris RV, Brearley A, Lauer HV, Treiman AH, Zolensky ME, Schwandt CS, Lofgren GE, McKay GA (2004) Evidence for exclusively inorganic formation of magnetite in Martian meteorite ALH84001. *American Mineralogist* 89(5-6):681–695. URL <https://doi.org/10.2138/am-2004-5-602>
- l) Chang L, Roberts AP, Williams W, Fitz Gerald JD, Larrasoña JC, Jovane L, Muxworthy AR (2012) Giant magnetofossils and hyperthermal events. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 351–352(0):258–269. URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2012.07.031>

Figure 2:

Simpson ET, Kasama T, Pósfai M, Buseck PR, Harrison RJ, Dunin-Borkowski RE (2005) Magnetic induction mapping of magnetite chains in magnetotactic bacteria at room temperature and close to the Verwey transition using electron holography. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 17:108–121. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/17/1/017>

Figure 3:

- a) Data from Egli R (2004) Characterization of individual rock magnetic components by analysis of remanence curves, 1. Unmixing natural sediments. *Studia Geophysica et Geodaetica* 48(2):391–446. URL <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:SGEG.0000020839.45304.6d>
- b) Data from Ludwig P, Egli R, Bishop S, Chernenko V, Frederichs T, Rugel G, Merchel S, Orgeira MJ (2013) Characterization of primary and secondary magnetite in marine sediment by combining chemical and magnetic unmixing techniques. *Global and Planetary Change* 110:321–339. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2013.08.018>
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- d) Isolated crystals: FORC diagram from magnetosomes dispersed in a clay— Egli R (2021) Magnetic characterization of geologic materials with first-order reversal curves. In: Franco V, Dodrill B, eds., *Magnetic Measurement Techniques for Material Characterization*. Springer, Cham. URL https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-70443-8_17
- d) Native and fold-collapsed 2-strand chains: FORC simulations— Amor M, Wan J, Egli R, Carlut J, Gatel C, Andersen IM, Snoeck E, Komeili A (2022) Key signatures of magnetofossils elucidated by mutant magnetotactic bacteria and micromagnetic calculations. *Journal Of Geophysical Research-Solid Earth* 127. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1029/2021JB023239>
- d) Loops: FORC diagram of mutant bacteria— Amor M, Wan J, Egli R, Carlut J, Gatel C, Andersen IM, Snoeck E, Komeili A (2022) Key signatures of magnetofossils elucidated by mutant magnetotactic bacteria and micromagnetic calculations. *Journal Of Geophysical Research-Solid Earth* 127. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1029/2021JB023239>
- d) Clusters: FORC diagram of mutant bacteria— Data from Katzmann E, Eibauer M, Lin W, Pan Y, Plitzko JM, Schu'ler D (2013) Analysis of magnetosome chains in magnetotactic bacteria by magnetic measurements and automated image analysis of electron micrographs. *Applied And Environmental Microbiology* 79. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1128/AEM.02143-13>

Figure 4:

Modified from Knoll AH, Bergmann KD, Strauss JV (2016) Life: The first two billion years. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 371(1707):20150493. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2015.0493>

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